
Green Selling Antecedents and their effects on Business Performance of Fast-Food firms in Port Harcourt, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the relationship between green selling and business performance of fast-food firms in Port Harcourt, Rivers State. In response to the growing environmental consciousness and the increasing emphasis on ecological business activities, firms are delving into green strategies as source of competitive advantage. Particularly, this study examines the effect of green innovation and eco-labeling on some of the critical performance metrics. The study adopted a cross-sectional research design and primary data were collected and analyzed to determine the extent of relationships among the study variables. The aftermath findings of the study shows that green selling practices, particularly green innovation and eco-labeling have significant and positive outcomes on business performance proxies on well as staff drive and organizational goodwill. The study concludes that adopting green selling strategies would enhance firm's performance and reinforce competitive positioning among fast-food firms. It therefore recommends that business executives and owners prioritize inventive and environmentally responsible reforms to improve organizational performance.

Keywords:

Green Selling, Business Performance, Green Innovation, Eco Labeling, Staff Drive, Goodwill.

1.0 Introduction

The fast-food industry has experienced substantial transformations, characterized by rapid service and a variety of innovative strategies. Schlosser (2012) highlighted the initiatives of leading global chains like McDonald's, KFC, and Burger King to maintain standardized operations while addressing health concerns through healthier menu options and enhanced nutritional transparency. Additionally, technological advancements such as mobile ordering, self-service kiosks, and data analytics have revolutionized operations, improving efficiency and customer experiences (Thompson, 2015). In Port Harcourt, the fast-food sector comprises both international brands and local chains, catering to a diverse clientele (Eze, 2017). Wharton et al. (2021) argued that 20% of food waste originates from consumers, and offering fresh products can

enhance profitability and performance. However, Beretta et al. (2017) identified food waste as a major challenge, with approximately 60% attributed to fast-food establishments, exacerbating climate change and environmental degradation.

Green Selling has emerged as a key focus, with firms incorporating environmental responsibility into their operations and marketing through green-themed logos, campaigns, and sustainable packaging. As environmental concerns rise, not all customers prioritize green products. Therefore, targeted marketing and a commitment to corporate social responsibility are critical for successful Green Selling (Carter, 2011). The pressure to act on climate change mitigation is growing for businesses globally. Recognizing how the values of fast food firms' owners and managers influence strategic choices is crucial, as individuals tend to make decisions that are consistent with their personal values (Gorgievski et al., 2021), and fast food firms' owners/managers tend to have more control over their firms compared to their counterparts in larger organizations. As such, their personal values can directly influence their firm's overall directions (Schaefer et al., 2020). Within fast food sector, green selling decisions are often driven by the values of their owners/managers (Schaefer et al., 2020).

Green Selling, which focuses on promoting eco-friendly products, has grown in popularity due to increased consumer concern for the environment. It involves using sustainable practices, eco-friendly packaging, and being transparent about product benefits (Ottman, 2011). Despite facing challenges like false claims and higher costs, Green Selling continues to rise, driven by consumer demand and regulations (Polonsky, 2020). Green Selling also faces challenges such as green washing, where companies deceptively promote products as environmentally friendly without substantial backing. Consumers and regulatory bodies have become more vigilant, prompting businesses to ensure their green claims are credible and supported by verifiable practices (Polonsky, 2020). As environmental concerns continue, the demand for Green Selling also rises, promoting environmentally safe goods and services that still meet consumer needs (Ansar, 2013). Over the last years, environmentalism has occurred to be an important business movement due to rising issues connected to depletion of the ozone layer, acid rains, and degradation of the land and many more pressing environmental issues (Dhiraj, 2014). Green Selling was measured using Green innovativeness (Hasan & Ali, 2015) and Eco labeling (Juwaheer & Pudarath, 2014), Green innovativeness which describes how the firm will adopt new technology, new products, new processes that are not harmful for consumption and to the environment and society at large.

Business Performance is the ability of the company to gain profit from its resources and achieves the objectives. However, the term business performance usually refers to the company's achievements measured using a number of metrics known as the key performance indicators (Arkadiusz, 2022). Business performance is analysing the company's performance against its objectives. It comprises the actual results or the outcome compared to the intended output or result. Indicators of business performance often include Staff Drive and Goodwill. Staff Drive captures the satisfaction, enthusiasm, and confidence employees feel in their workplace, directly influencing productivity, innovativeness, and retention rates. According to Herzberg (2012), high Staff Drive fosters a positive workplace culture, which in turn enhances organizational outcomes. On the other hand, Goodwill represents an intangible yet crucial asset, derived from a company's reputation, brand equity, and customer loyalty. Goodwill facilitates the development of strong

customer relationships, attracts new business, and ensures long-term profitability. Together, Staff Drive and Goodwill are vital in assessing a firm's sustainability and competitiveness, as noted by Kaplan and Norton (2013).

Moreover, environmental problems such as environmental pollution and degradation, excessive wastes disposal, climate change and global warming have changed the purchasing patterns of customers as many customers are now demanding for green products that do not only meet their immediate needs but will also preserve the environment from damage, however causing business performance to decline in terms goodwill and staff drive. The aim of this study was to empirically ascertain the relationship between Green Selling and Business performance of fast food firms in Port Harcourt. Specifically, the objectives were to;

- i. Ascertain the relationship between green innovativeness and Staff drive.
- ii. Determine the relationship between green innovativeness and goodwill.
- iii. Investigate the relationship between eco labelling and Staff drive.
- iv. Explore the relationship between eco labelling and goodwill.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Green Selling

Green Selling, also referred to as environmental marketing, ecological marketing, and sustainable marketing (Qureshi & Mehraj, 2021), has evolved over the years into a broader concept known as sustainable marketing. In the 70's and 80's, the marketing literature extensively explored environmental problems, yet both consumers and enterprises showed minimal interest in these issues. Green Selling involves product modifications, changes in production processes, packaging adjustments, and modifications in advertising methods (Qureshi & Mehraj, 2021). Grant (2007) highlights Green Selling as a recent focus in business, representing a strategic marketing approach that gained momentum in the late 20th century. Nistoreanu et al. (2020), noted that the practice of Green Selling is steadily increasing due to growing consumer interest in sustainability and the demand for eco-friendly products. Green Selling focuses on developing goods and services that satisfy customer needs and desires while ensuring that marketing practices, including promotion, pricing, and distribution, do not have negative impacts on individuals, society, the environment, or future generations (Govender & Govender, 2016). Green Selling involves various actions, from production to post-purchase services, aiming to balance profits and environmental protection (Gordon et al., 2011). Furthermore, Green Selling offers significant opportunities to minimize environmental problems caused by societal, political, and economic factors, with increasing pressure on businesses to acknowledge and take responsibility for the environmental impacts of their operations, Green Selling has evolved into a concept seen as an imminent moral obligation (Govender & Govender, 2016).

2.2 Business Performance

Business Performance is a frequently used and dynamic concept that signifies achieving a task with efficiency and effectiveness beyond existing standards. Business performance is the overall success of the company in achieving the strategic goals that have been set by the company. These strategic goals are planned through the company's vision, mission and strategy. Business Performance is the result of management activities in utilizing its resources, (Blake, 2017).

Performance measurement is an effort made to measure the level of success of business activities based on predetermined standards and criteria, as well as how the level of achievement of company success is in accordance with the target, so that irregularities that occur can be eliminated through a process of continuous improvement. Business performance refers to the level at which a business is carrying out its activities and also, competing. It can also be used interchangeably with firm performance or just performance. Hasan & Ali (2015) defines firm performance from perceived benefits perspective which may be achieved through integration of environmental management in their business operations.

2.2.1. Staff Drive

In organizational research, the relationship between morale and performance was a significant topic. Staff drive is essential for ensuring high engagement and productivity while reducing turnover and absenteeism costs. By investing in Staff drive, organizations can enhance workers' enthusiasm and overall attitude towards their jobs, leading to improved performance. Staff drive refers to the attitude, satisfaction, and overall outlook of employees during their time with a company or business. Employees who are satisfied and motivated typically have higher morale than those who are not. Employee engagement and satisfaction are crucial for ensuring workers are happy within their organization (Egwuonwu, 2011). Blake (2017) emphasized that morale is an emotional feeling, It reflects how an employee feels about their job, their boss, and the company they work for. High morale often leads to increased motivation and productivity, while low morale can result in dissatisfaction and decreased performance. Morale is influenced by various factors, including workplace environment, recognition, and support from management. Blake (2017) highlighted that good morale, job satisfaction, and loyalty lead to a positive attitude in employees, improving their performance.

2.2.2. Goodwill

Schwaiger (2004) emphasized that a positive goodwill can be assessed through the use of good corporate image. Goodwill has become an increasingly important asset on balance sheets from 1990 to 2007 (Li & Sloan, 2014). Goodwill, in a business context, refers to the intangible value that a company possesses beyond its tangible assets and liabilities. It encompasses aspects like brand image, customer loyalty, business ethics, and the overall perception of the company by its stakeholders. This intangible asset often results in higher sales volumes, customer retention, and the ability to charge premium prices (Egwuonwu, 2011). Studies indicate that a strong corporate reputation allows companies to charge higher prices for their products or services (Egwuonwu, 2011). In other words, organizations with better reputations tend to place higher price tags on their offerings compared to those with lower reputations. Ghose and Yang, (2009) highlighted that while a good reputation enhances corporate performance, a negative reputation can be more detrimental than the benefits gained from a positive one which emphasized that a strong corporate reputation significantly boosts Business performance.

2.3. Green Selling and Business Performance

Green Selling is defined as an enterprise's marketing activities associated with its ethical and social responsibility requirements (Dheeraj & Vishal, 2012). Green et al. (2012) mentioned the

positive impacts of harmonizing Green Selling strategies on the supply chain particularly and the marketing activities of firms in general, thereby improving firm financial performance. Green product images include products with environmentally friendly features, recyclability, and green package. It involves incorporating sustainability and environmental considerations into a variety of marketing techniques such as product design, packaging, delivery, and promotions (Kwarto et al., 2022). Green marketing is the practice of promoting products that are deemed sustainable for the environment (Alikor et al., 2022). Thus, an extensive variety of operations, including product alterations, production process adjustments, packaging modifications, and advertising alterations, are included in green marketing (Okoli et al., 2022). Green marketing comprises developing and advertising products and services that simultaneously satisfy consumers' demands for efficiency, quality, and cost. Green marketing is an organisational approach that successfully and sustainably finds out, predicts, and meets client and social demands while taking environmental factors into account (Gusov et al., 2022).

2.3.1 Green Innovativeness and Business Performance

Green innovativeness emerged as a significant focus in academic research during the 90's. However, scholars have not agreed on a single definition. Andersen (2008) suggests that environmental (green) innovativeness research is still in its early stages, with few researchers dedicated to studying environmental issues in innovativeness management. Beise and Rennings, (2005) describe green innovativeness as the implementation of new technologies, processes, and products aimed at preventing or reducing environmental damage. Expanding on this definition, Akbari et al. (2022) argued that green innovativeness can reduce environmental pollution, conserve energy, and promote sustainable development by aligning environmental protection with corporate competitiveness. It's no longer just about creating something new, but also about addressing a wide range of challenges. Innovativeness can be categorized into two types: incremental innovativeness and radical innovativeness. Incremental innovativeness involves enhancing existing products or processes by introducing new improvements gradually, resulting in short-term changes and meeting market demands (Chen et al., 2016). On the other hand, radical or disruptive innovativeness entails creating entirely new products or services that are unprecedented in the market, requiring substantial investments, research, and development (Souto, 2015). Consequently, this hypotheses was formulated:

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between Green innovativeness and Staff drive of fast food firms in Port Harcourt.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between Green innovativeness and Goodwill of fast food firms in Port Harcourt.

2.3.2. Eco Labelling and Business Performance

In response to the rising consumer demand for healthier, safer, and more environmentally friendly food products, Eco labelling has gained significant importance in recent years. Eco-labels are attractive tools that inform customers about the potential environmental impact of their purchasing decisions (Orsato, 2009). Eco-labelling, introduced in the late 70's, aids consumers in making environmentally conscious purchases. Eco-labels aim to educate consumers about a

product's environmental impact and promote environmental protection by encouraging them to choose products with less impact. They identify a product or service's overall environmental impact based on its lifecycle (Bratt, et, al. 2011). Introduced in the early 80's, eco-labels communicate environmental management efforts. An eco-label is a symbol placed on green product packaging or included in product information, indicating the extent to which the product supports environmentally friendly outcomes (Struwig & Adendorff, 2018). Eco-labeling is important not because of its closeness to other stakeholders in the value chain but for its direct impact on the environment (Sarkis, 2018). Thus, the researchers proposed the following hypotheses:

H₃: There is no significant relationship between Eco-labelling and Staff drive of fast food firms in Port Harcourt.

H₄: There is no significant relationship between Eco labeling and Goodwill of fast food firms in Port Harcourt.

2.4 Theoretical Framework: Bio-Ecological Theory

The bio-ecological theory was born out of the system theory which proposes that man does not live alone but with interrelated systems. The bio-ecological theory is credited to a respected American Psychologist known as Bronfenbrenner who studied the dependency between human and environment. His study of ecology and human development in 1979 revealed the importance of the environment in human development (Härkönen, 2007). Bronfenbrenner (2004) defined ecological theory as the study of human development in perspective of enduring environment. The theory opines that child's development is as a result of enduring environment which are subdivide into upper and supportive layers. Bronfenbrenner and Ceci (2004) noted that the framework of the model focuses on the importance of understanding bidirectional influences between human development and their surrounding environments. Paquette and Ryan (2021) pointed out that ecology has changed our society as we are so engaged with protecting our physical environment against problems from technology even though we have not done enough in the securing our social life. The theory was expressed to show the relationship between human behavior and its influencers. The theory can be stated thus: $B = f(PE)$. Where B = Behavior, P = Person, and E = Environment. Bronfenbrenner adopted this model to form a new formula for development as thus: $D = f(PE)$ where D = Development. In summary, the bio-ecological theory shows the relationship between human and its environment. Human needs the environment to survive and the environment needs the human to survive. In relation to green brand strategies, business organizations follow these theoretical frameworks to engage in branding efforts in order to enhance environmental wellbeing.

2.3. Empirical Review

Lay et al. (2025) investigated drivers of strategic green marketing orientation: An SME owner-manager perspective, SMEs are crucial in addressing climate change as they constitute more than 90% of global businesses. Through a survey involving 426 SME owners/managers in the United States, it reveals that SME owners/managers' biospheric values positively influence SGMO via perceived competitive advantage, which in turns influence business performance. It also identifies

perceived stakeholder pressures, perceived behavioral control, and perceived risks as key boundary conditions on the relationship between SGMO and its drivers.

Barnabas et al. (2024) investigated Green Marketing Strategies and Business Performance: A Tool for Good Governance. The study sample size is fifty (50) and data was obtained through questionnaire. Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 21, was used to analyse the data while Pearson correlation was used to test the research hypotheses. The independent variable green Marketing strategy has two dimensions while the dependent variable is business performance. The result revealed a significant and positive relationship between green price and business performance. Furthermore, the result also showed that the relationship between green products and business performance is significantly positive.

Samson (2023) examined the effect of green marketing practices on environmental performance at Kisumu Water and Sewerage Company in Kisumu Kenya (KIWASCO). The study is guided by the stakeholder's theory in correlation study design. The study population constituted 181 employees of KIWASCO, out of which a sample of 25 respondents was drawn using a proportionate stratified sampling technique. Pilot results showed a reliability test of Cronbach's Alpha coefficient between 0.701 and 0.777. The findings revealed that green marketing practices collectively accounted for 55.6% ($R^2 = 0.556$, $p = 0.000$) variation in environmental performance at KIWASCO. It was further revealed that dimensions of sustainable green products ($B = 0.466$, $p = 0.001$) and sustainable distribution ($B = 0.343$, $p = 0.000$) both had significant positive influence on environmental performance at KIWASCO.

Obafemi and Ihunwo (2022) examined the relationship between green marketing practices and business wellness, in the Nigerian food and beverages firms. The target population for this study was twelve (12) food and beverages firms domiciled in Rivers State, with 60 respondents drawn from the management of the sampled firms. A self-administered structured questionnaire was used to collect primary data and the data obtained were accordingly analyzed using Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficient Statistical Tool to test the hypotheses with the aid of Special Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20.0. The result revealed that there is significant and positive relationship between green marketing practices and business wellness of Nigerian food and beverages firms; while innovativeness moderates the impact on green marketing practices and business wellness.

Omofowa & Omofowa (2022) examined the influence of green innovation strategy, information technology and entrepreneurial innovativeness on business performance, using the green business, model innovation perspective. The authors surveyed 360 employees in 30 manufacturing companies operating in Nigeria. Data from 360 employees' reveal that green innovation strategy, information technology and entrepreneurial innovativeness significantly impact business performance. Further, these results clarify the role of the influence of Green Innovation Strategy Information technology and Entrepreneurial Innovativeness plays in fostering business performance in the emerging market context.

3.0 Methodology

Research Design: This study adopted a cross-sectional research design, which is appropriate for capturing data at a single point in time across selected fast-food firms in Port Harcourt. The

population for this study consists of employees, top managers, and customers of selected fast-food firms in Port Harcourt. As of Jan 2024, records from the Rivers State Ministry of Commerce and Industry show 65 registered fast-food firms in Port Harcourt. For this study, 20 fast-food firms will be chosen based on logistical considerations, geographic clustering, and proximity to the researcher. To select this population, the study employed a non-probability sampling approach, utilizing both convenience sampling and purposive sampling techniques. Convenience Sampling enables the researcher to select firms based on their accessibility, reducing travel time and associated costs. A purposive sampling technique was employed, focusing on companies' directors, employees and customer-base that have experience or insights into Green Selling practices, ensuring that relevant perspectives are included in the data collection process (Palinkas, et. al. 2015). A sample of approximately 200 employees of respective companies, 20 top Managers from the 20 fast food firms and 90 customers from respective fast food firms, in addition Managers, employees and customer-base are expected to fill the questionnaire and validate the responses from each respective focus group which shall be drawn. This study questionnaire is design to collect same data from different respondents. A total of 400 sample size.

Method of Data Analysis: Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to determine the difference in responses between employees, managers and customer based on Business Performance regarding Green Selling practices of fast-food firms in Port Harcourt.

4.0 Results and Discussion

In this study, a total of four hundred (400) copies of questionnaire were distributed, out of which three hundred and eighty two (382) were duly complete and retrieved and making a response rate of 99.5%. Focusing on the gender distribution of the respondents, 30.4% of the respondents are males, while 69.6% of the respondents are females. This implies that majority of the participants that participated in the survey are females. According to their age distribution, 16.8% of the respondents were within the age range of 20-29years, 39.8% of the respondents' age ranges were within 30-39 years, and 37.2% of the respondents' age ranges were within 40-49years, while 6.2% of the respondents are 50 years and above. Also, the distribution of the respondents according to their education qualification shows that, 4.5% of the respondents had O'level certificates, 8.4% of the respondents had NCE/OND academic degree, 62.5% of the respondents had HND/B.Sc., and 19.4% of the respondents had MBA/M.Sc, while 5.2% of the respondents had Ph.D/DBA degree.

4.1 Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between green innovation and staff drive of fast food firms in Port Harcourt.

Table 1: Correlation Analysis Showing the Relationship between Green innovation and Staff drive

Correlations			
		Green innovation	Staff drive
Green innovation	Pearson Correlation	1	.843
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	382	382
Staff drive	Pearson Correlation	.843	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	382	382
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).			

Interpretation: Table 1 shows the Pearson correlation result, indicating the relationship between green innovation and staff drive of fast food firms in Port Harcourt, it shows that $r = 0.843$, $p(0.00) < 0.05$ at 5% level of significance, thus indicating that there is a strong and positive relationship between green innovation and staff drive of fast food firms in Port Harcourt, Also, at $r^2 = 0.711$ which indicated that the coefficient of determination of the correlation between green innovation and staff drive of fast food firms in Port Harcourt was 71.1%, implying that green innovation has a high and strong correlation with staff drive of fast food firms in Port Harcourt while 28.9% explained others factors outside the model. This result indicates that 71.1% increase in green innovation will proportionately increase the function of staff drive; as such the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternative was accepted and this states that there is a significant relationship between green innovation and staff drive of fast food firms in Port Harcourt.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between green innovation and goodwill of fast food firms in Port Harcourt.

Table 2: Correlation Analysis Showing the Relationship between Green innovation and Goodwill

Correlations			
		Green innovation	Goodwill
Green innovation	Pearson Correlation	1	.888
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	382	382
Goodwill	Pearson Correlation	.888	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	382	382
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).			

Interpretation: Table 2 shows the Pearson correlation result, indicating the relationship between green innovation and goodwill of fast food firms in Port Harcourt, it shows that $r = 0.888$, $p(0.00) < 0.05$ at 5% level of significance, thus indicating that there is a strong and positive relationship between green innovation and goodwill of fast food firms in Port Harcourt, Also, at $r^2 = 0.789$ which indicated that the coefficient of determination of the correlation between green innovation and goodwill of fast food firms in Port Harcourt was 78.9%, implying that green innovation has a high and strong correlation with goodwill of fast food firms in Port Harcourt while 21.1% explained others factors outside the model. This result indicates that 78.9% increase in green innovation will proportionately increase the function of goodwill vice versa, as such the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternative was accepted and this states that there is a significant relationship between green innovation and goodwill of fast food firms in Port Harcourt.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant relationship between eco labelling and staff drive of fast food firms in Port Harcourt.

Table 3 Correlation Analysis showing the relationship between eco labelling and staff drive

Correlations			
		Eco labelling	Staff drive
Eco labelling	Pearson Correlation	1	.877
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	382	382
Staff drive	Pearson Correlation	.877	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	382	382
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).			

Interpretation: Table 3 shows the Pearson correlation result, indicating the relationship between eco labelling and staff drive of fast food firms in Port Harcourt, it shows that $r = 0.877$, $p(0.00) < 0.05$ at 5% level of significance, thus indicating that there is a strong and positive relationship between eco labelling and staff drive of fast food firms in Port Harcourt, Also, at $r^2 = 0.769$ which indicated that the coefficient of determination of the correlation between eco labelling and staff drive of fast food firms in Port Harcourt was 87.7%, implying that eco labelling has a high and strong correlation with staff drive of fast food firms in Port Harcourt while 12.3% explained others factors outside the model. This result indicates that 87.7% increase in eco labelling will proportionately increase the function of staff drive vice versa, as such the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternative was accepted and this states that there is a significant relationship between eco labelling and staff drive of fast food firms in Port Harcourt.

Hypothesis Four: There is no significant relationship between eco labelling and goodwill of fast food firms in Port Harcourt.

Table 4. Correlation Analysis Showing the Relationship Between Eco labelling and Goodwill

Correlations			
		Eco labelling	Goodwill
Eco labelling	Pearson Correlation	1	.869
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	382	382
Goodwill	Pearson Correlation	.869	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	382	382
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).			

Interpretation: table 4 shows the Pearson correlation result, indicating the relationship between eco labelling and goodwill of fast food firms in Port Harcourt, it shows that $r = 0.869$, $p(0.00) < 0.05$ at 5% level of significance, thus indicating that there is a strong and positive relationship between eco labelling and goodwill of fast food firms in Port Harcourt, Also, at $r^2 = 0.755$ which indicated that the coefficient of determination of the correlation between eco labelling and goodwill of fast food firms in Port Harcourt was 75.5%, implying that eco labelling has a high and strong correlation with goodwill of fast food firms in Port Harcourt while 24.5% explained others factors outside the model. This result indicates that 75.5% increase in eco labelling will proportionately increase the function of goodwill vice versa, as such the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternative was accepted and this states that there is a significant relationship between eco labelling and goodwill of fast food firms in Port Harcourt.

4.2: Discussion of Findings

This part of the study sought to discuss the various findings pertaining to the analysis of data presentation and findings as they were above.

1. Correlation between Green innovation and Staff Drive

Hypothesis one (H_{01}) aimed at examine the significant relationship between green innovation and staff drive towards fast food firms in Port Harcourt. The outputs from PPMCC revealed a positive of 0.843 and 71.1% relationship between green innovation and staff drive of fast food firms in Port Harcourt. This suggests a positive and strong relationship between the variables. This shows that staff drive is a positive function of green innovation. This means that, if green innovation improves by 1%, staff drive as well will improve by same 1% and vice versa. This implies that there is statistically significant, indicating a statistical evidence against H_{01} . Therefore, we reject hypothesis one, leading us to conclude that green innovation has a positive and strong significant relationship with staff drive of fast food firms in Port Harcourt. Some empirical results agreed with our findings, such like, Obafemi and Ihunwo (2022) study revealed a positive correlation effect. Others empirical research exploring the relationship between eco-environmental innovation and firm performance presented mixed findings (Omofowa & Omofowa, 2022).

2. Correlation between Green innovation and Goodwill

Hypothesis two (H_{02}) states that green innovation does not have significant nexus with goodwill towards fast food firms in Port Harcourt. The result from Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient revealed a positive relationship of 0.888 and 78.9% between green innovation and goodwill towards fast food firms in Port Harcourt. The output shows strong relationship between green innovation and goodwill towards fast food firms in Port Harcourt. This result further revealed that goodwill is a positive function of green innovation. As evidenced in Table 4.9, the P-value has an estimated value of 0.000 which was lesser than 0.05. This implies also it is statistically significant, indicating a statistical evidence against H_{02} . This means that, if green innovation improve by 1%, goodwill as well will improve by same 1% and vice versa. Therefore, the researcher rejected hypothesis two, leading us to conclude that green innovation has a significant nexus with goodwill towards fast food firms in Port Harcourt. Some empirical results agreed with our findings, such like, Obafemi and Ihunwo (2022) study revealed a positive correlation effect. Others empirical research exploring the relationship between eco-environmental innovation and firm performance presented mixed findings (Omofowa & Omofowa, 2022).

3. Correlation between Eco labelling and Staff Drive

Hypothesis three (H_{03}) aimed at examine the significant relationship between eco labelling and staff drive toward fast food firms in Port Harcourt. The outputs from PPMCC revealed a positive of 0.877 and 76.9% relationship between eco labelling and staff drive towards fast food firms in Port Harcourt. This suggests a strong relationship between the variables. This suggests a positive and strong relationship between the variables. This shows that staff drive is a positive function of eco labelling. It also revealed that 1% of eco labelling improvement lead to 1% improvement on staff drive. This implies that there is statistically significant, indicating a statistical evidence against H_{03} . Therefore, we rejected hypothesis three, leading us to conclude that eco labelling has a significant relationship with staff drive towards fast food firms in Port Harcourt. The following studies agreed with our findings: Lay et al. (2025) results showed that green brand positioning, while does not influence attitude toward green brand, has positive effects on green brand knowledge. Green brand knowledge positively influences attitude toward green brand, and finally, attitude toward green brand positively influence green purchase intention.

4. Correlation between Eco labelling and Goodwill

Hypothesis four (H_{04}) states that eco labelling does not have significant nexus with goodwill towards fast food firms in Port Harcourt. The result from PPMCC revealed a positive relationship of 0.869 and 75.5% between eco labelling and goodwill towards fast food firms in Port Harcourt. The output shows strong relationship between eco labelling and goodwill towards fast food firms in Port Harcourt. This suggests a positive and strong relationship between the variables. This shows that goodwill is a positive function of eco labelling. This result further revealed that goodwill is a positive function of eco labelling. It also revealed that 1% of eco labelling improvement lead to 1% improvement on goodwill. The results further shows that, the P-value has an estimated value of 0.000 which was lesser than 0.05. This implies also it is statistically significant, indicating statistical evidence against H_{04} . Therefore, the researcher rejected hypothesis four, leading us to conclude that eco labelling has a significant nexus with goodwill

towards fast food firms in Port Harcourt. Our findings revealed a significant implication of eco labelling on business performance through goodwill. The following studies agreed with our findings: Lay et al. (2025) results showed that green brand positioning, while does not influence attitude toward green brand, has positive effects on green brand knowledge. Green brand knowledge positively influences attitude toward green brand, and finally, attitude toward green brand positively influence green purchase intention.

5.1 Conclusion and Recommendations

This study, which evaluated the effects of green selling and business performance of fast food firms, concludes that there exists positive correlation between green selling and business performance. The results on the relationship between green innovation and business performance (staff drive, and goodwill) indicated strong and positive correlation. Premised on the second research questions; the study concludes that a strong and positive significant relationship exists between biospheric value and business performance (staff drive, and goodwill) of fast food firms in Port Harcourt.

Based on the findings and the conclusion reached in this study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. The creation and development of green selling strategies such as eco-labelling should be purpose driven, having clearly outline objectives,
- ii. The development of green innovation should focus on creating strong visibility and environmental presence.
- iii. Government as a matter of necessity should engage all stakeholders to ensure implementation of policies that will ensure strict adherence to environmental regulations.
- iv. The fast food firms in Rivers State and beyond should develop green crusade that will focus on creating strong visibility and environmental consciousness among stakeholders.
- v. Fast food firms must be flexible and swift in catching up with trends in climate change, global warming, clean technology and green consumer behavior.

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